

Innovating Quick Commerce Logistics: The Swiggy Instamart Model for Grocery Delivery in Coimbatore

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Abstract

This study investigates the operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and logistics innovations of Swiggy Instamart's quick commerce (Q-commerce) model in Coimbatore. With the growing need for ultra-fast grocery delivery in Tier-2 cities, the research surveyed 150 customers, 30 delivery executives, and 10 logistics managers using structured questionnaires. Findings reveal that 60% of customers rated Swiggy's delivery speed 4 or 5 on a satisfaction scale, and 55% were satisfied with product availability. Regression analysis showed that delivery speed and app usability were strong predictors of overall customer satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.61$). GIS mapping identified high-order density zones such as Gandhipuram and Peelamedu, highlighting the strategic need for more dark stores in East Coimbatore. Comparative analysis showed that 48% of users preferred Swiggy over competitors like Blinkit and Zepto. While Swiggy leads in delivery time and user interface satisfaction, operational challenges such as traffic congestion and order delays remain. The study concludes that Swiggy Instamart's AI-driven inventory system and dark store model are instrumental in achieving rapid delivery, but continuous improvement in logistics and customer experience is necessary for long-term sustainability and competitiveness in the Q-commerce space.

Keywords: Quick Commerce, Swiggy Instamart, Grocery Delivery, Logistics Efficiency, Customer Satisfaction, Dark Stores, Urban Retail, Coimbatore, Delivery Speed, Hyperlocal Supply Chain

INTRODUCTION

The grocery retail landscape in India is undergoing a significant transformation driven by evolving consumer behavior, increased smartphone penetration, and the demand for instant convenience. One of the most notable developments in this space is the rise of Quick Commerce (Q-commerce), a model that promises grocery and household item delivery within 10–30 minutes. This business model builds upon the foundation of e-commerce, leveraging hyperlocal logistics, dark stores, and mobile app interfaces to provide unparalleled speed and convenience to urban consumers.

The COVID-19 pandemic served as a catalyst in accelerating the shift toward digital grocery delivery platforms. Consumer habits shifted from bulk, planned purchases to need-based, on-

demand buying behavior. This change has particularly benefited platforms like Swiggy Instamart, which rapidly expanded its reach by optimizing delivery routes, investing in AI-driven inventory management, and developing a dense network of dark stores to meet time-sensitive demands.

Coimbatore, a rapidly developing Tier-2 city in Tamil Nadu, has become a fertile ground for testing and scaling such innovative delivery models. Its growing urban population, increasing digital literacy, and traffic conditions offer both opportunities and challenges for quick commerce platforms aiming to balance speed, accuracy, and cost-efficiency.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1 INTRODUCTION TO QUICK COMMERCE (Q-COMMERCE)

The evolution from traditional e-commerce to Q-commerce represents a paradigm shift in consumer behavior, logistics, and digital retail. E-commerce, traditionally focused on scheduled deliveries, has transitioned to rapid-response systems, primarily driven by consumer need for immediacy. Ranjekar & Roy (2023) highlight how the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated this shift, reinforcing the demand for faster access to essential items. Gund and Daniel (2024) describe Q-commerce as the natural progression of e-commerce, where time efficiency becomes the primary differentiator.

Q-commerce is defined as the ultra-fast delivery of a small selection of goods, particularly groceries and household items, within a window of 10–30 minutes. Its success hinges on hyperlocal delivery networks, app-driven platforms, AI-enabled inventory systems, and strategic warehouse placement. According to Prakash (2024), urban consumers prioritize convenience, ease of access, and immediate fulfillment, making Q-commerce an increasingly preferred model. Scripown (2023) further explains that Q-commerce aligns with the digital expectations of metropolitan and Tier-1 city residents, positioning it as an integral part of the evolving retail ecosystem.

The Growth of Q-Commerce in India

India's Q-commerce market has grown significantly post-2020, fueled by digital literacy, smartphone penetration, and evolving consumer lifestyles. According to BRAC University (2023), Q-commerce app usage in metropolitan and Tier-1 cities grew by over 150%, indicating a sharp shift toward spontaneous and need-based buying. Major players in the Indian Q-commerce space include Swiggy

Instamart, Zepto, Blinkit, and Dunzo. Swiggy's competitive advantage lies in its robust logistics infrastructure and the synergy with its food delivery network (WareIQ, 2024).

The Indian Q-commerce sector, however, faces multiple challenges. Gund & Daniel (2024) identify scalability issues, high delivery costs, and workforce attrition as primary constraints. Euromonitor (2023) suggests that market expansion to Tier-2 and Tier-3 cities—through localized warehousing and vernacular app versions—may offer a sustainable path for long-term growth.

Swiggy Instamart: Business Model and Operations

Swiggy Instamart's operational framework is built around a dense network of dark stores, real-time order management, and data-driven logistics. RevBoosters (2023) describe Swiggy's use of AI and predictive analytics to achieve sub-30-minute delivery windows. These dark stores—essentially micro-warehouses—are strategically located to reduce delivery time and ensure SKU availability. SAGE Case (2023) notes that dark stores typically stock 2,000–3,000 high-demand items, enabling high inventory turnover and precision restocking.

To manage inventory efficiently, Swiggy employs automated inventory tracking and machine learning models for demand forecasting. These tools minimize stockouts and improve accuracy in order fulfillment (ScienceDirect, 2024; WareIQ, 2024). This tech-driven approach contributes significantly to Swiggy's superior delivery performance in urban clusters.

Consumer Behaviour and Preferences in Q-Commerce Grocery Delivery

Consumer preferences in Q-commerce are shaped by time sensitivity,

convenience, app interface, and product availability. A Bangalore-based study (Prakash, 2024) found that consumers favored Q-commerce platforms over traditional grocery options due to their faster and more predictable delivery schedules.

While price remains a consideration, a significant proportion of urban middle-class users are willing to pay a premium for the convenience offered by Q-commerce (IIMA, 2023). However, frequency of repeat orders is often moderated by price sensitivity (Gund & Daniel, 2024). According to Tandfonline (2023), customer expectations are focused on order accuracy, real-time tracking, and efficient support—factors that directly influence platform loyalty.

Logistics and Last-Mile Delivery Innovations in Q-Commerce

AI and machine learning are at the heart of Q-commerce logistics optimization. Swiggy uses dynamic routing algorithms, predictive demand models, and real-time delivery assignment tools to manage operations (RevBoosters, 2023). Route planning systems account for traffic, weather, and customer location to optimize delivery paths and reduce turnaround times (HP Gund et al., 2024).

However, challenges in last-mile delivery persist. These include address inaccuracies, customer unavailability, and traffic-related delays. Roy & Ranjekar (2023) suggest that innovations such as geolocation tagging and localized delivery hubs could help resolve these bottlenecks.

Sustainability and Environmental Impact of Q-Commerce

Environmental sustainability remains a concern in Q-commerce due to excessive packaging and frequent vehicle usage. Gund & Daniel (2024) estimate that smaller basket sizes and higher delivery frequency contribute to greater emissions

compared to traditional retail. In response, Swiggy and Zepto have initiated eco-friendly programs including the adoption of electric vehicles and biodegradable packaging (IGI Global, 2024).

Smart supply chains, improved inventory accuracy, and consolidation of deliveries are some of the sustainable practices being adopted across the sector (ScienceDirect, 2024). These practices not only reduce carbon footprints but also enhance long-term efficiency.

Challenges and Future Trends in Q-Commerce Logistics

Despite its rapid growth, Q-commerce struggles with profitability and operational consistency. According to SSRN (2024), aggressive discounting and subsidized delivery models threaten the long-term financial viability of the sector. Regulatory frameworks, labor laws, and urban infrastructure limitations further complicate operations.

The future of Q-commerce in Tier-2 cities like Coimbatore looks promising. With localized adaptation, improved technology deployment, and sustainable practices, Q-commerce has the potential to become the default grocery procurement method in urban India (Scripown, 2023). The key to scalability lies in logistics innovation, customer-centric design, and operational sustainability.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

While Q-commerce platforms like Swiggy Instamart are gaining traction, sustaining logistics efficiency and customer satisfaction in Tier-2 cities like Coimbatore remains challenging.

Specific issues include inconsistent delivery performance, inventory limitations, and infrastructural constraints.

There is a need for in-depth regional analysis to understand the strengths and limitations of Swiggy's

logistics operations and its comparative performance against competitors such as Blinkit and Zepto.

Despite its promising potential, the scalability, sustainability, and customer retention strategies of Q-commerce in non-metro regions are underexplored.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

To analyze the logistics framework of Swiggy Instamart in Coimbatore and how it enables efficient Q-commerce

To identify key operational challenges and opportunities for growth in quick commerce grocery delivery.

To evaluate the effectiveness of Swiggy Instamart's dark store model and inventory management in improving delivery efficiency.

To assess customer satisfaction and service quality in Swiggy Instamart's delivery process.

To explore the future scope of Q-commerce logistics in India and recommend improvements based on industry trends.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research adopted a mixed-method approach to analyze the operational framework, logistics performance, and customer satisfaction of Swiggy Instamart in Coimbatore. The methodology integrates quantitative data collection from customers and delivery executives, along with qualitative insights from logistics managers to offer a comprehensive view of the quick commerce (Q-commerce) ecosystem.

Research Design

A descriptive and comparative research design was employed. Quantitative data were collected through structured questionnaires targeting key stakeholders—customers, delivery executives, and logistics managers. Thematic content analysis was used for

qualitative responses to identify patterns and operational insights.

Sampling Methodology

Population:

Residents of Coimbatore who are users of Swiggy Instamart, Swiggy delivery executives, and logistics/operations managers affiliated with Swiggy Instamart in Coimbatore.

Sample Size:

150 customers

30 delivery executives

10 logistics managers or partners

Sampling Technique:

For customers: Stratified random sampling was used. The customer base was divided into strata based on frequency of usage—frequent, occasional, and first-time users—to ensure representation across behavior patterns.

For delivery executives and Dlogistics managers: Purposive sampling was used to select participants with relevant operational experience in Q-commerce logistics.

Data Collection Tools

Questionnaires: Structured and semi-structured questionnaires were used for data collection. Separate sets were designed for each stakeholder group:

Customer Questionnaire
(Demographics, Usage Behavior, Satisfaction Metrics)

Delivery Executive Questionnaire
(Delivery Patterns, Operational Challenges)

Logistics Manager Questionnaire
(Inventory Practices, Demand Forecasting, Operational Insights)

Mode of Collection:

Customers: Google Forms and offline surveys

Delivery Executives: In-person interviews

Managers: In-depth interviews

Variables and Metrics

The key independent variables analysed included:

- Delivery time
- Product availability
- App experience
- Order accuracy
- Customer support

The primary dependent variable was:

- Customer Satisfaction

DATA ANALYSIS METHODS

- **Descriptive Statistics:** Used to summarize and visualize data on customer satisfaction, delivery time, and order accuracy.
- **Comparative Analysis:** Swiggy's logistics performance was compared with Blinkit and Zepto based on customer feedback.
- **Regression Analysis:** Explored how variables like delivery time, app usability, and product availability influence overall satisfaction.
- **Time Series Analysis:** Identified peak order periods and seasonal trends affecting operational planning.
- **GIS Mapping:** Google Maps-based visualization helped identify high-demand areas, delivery zones, and optimal locations for new dark stores.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This section presents the findings derived from a structured analysis of

responses collected from customers (n=150), delivery executives (n=30), and logistics managers (n=10). Stratified random sampling of customers ensured representation across three usage strata: frequent (n=60), occasional (n=60), and first-time users (n=30). The analysis is categorized under five key analytical frameworks: Descriptive Statistics, Comparative Analysis, Regression Analysis, Time Series Analysis, and GIS Mapping.

Descriptive Statistics

Key performance indicators were evaluated across customer experience and operational metrics.

Metric	Mean Score (1–5)	% Rating 4 or 5
Delivery Time	4.2	66%
Product Availability	3.8	58%
Order Accuracy	4.1	62%
App Experience	4.3	71%
Customer Support	3.7	52%

Frequent users rated delivery time highest (avg. 4.5), while first-time users reported the lowest satisfaction with product availability (avg. 3.4).

24% of respondents reported occasional issues such as late deliveries or missing items.

Comparative Analysis

Customer feedback was used to benchmark Swiggy Instamart against Blinkit and Zepto on key logistics parameters.

Platform	Delivery Speed (avg. mins)	Inventory Accuracy (%)	Overall Satisfaction Score
Swiggy Instamart	17.5	93%	4.2
Zepto	19.8	89%	3.9
Blinkit	20.3	86%	3.7

48% of customers ranked Swiggy as “better” or “much better” than competitors.

Areas where Swiggy excelled included app interface and fulfillment speed, while improvement was suggested in stock variety.

Time Series Analysis

Order volume data were analysed over a rolling 4-week period.

Peak hours: 6:00 PM – 9:00 PM (42% of orders)

Highest demand days: Fridays and Sundays

Seasonal trend: +27% increase in order volume during festival weeks (e.g., Pongal and Diwali)

Insights:

Dark store inventory needed reinforcement between 5:00 PM and 10:00 PM.

Staffing adjustments were implemented to reduce fulfillment lag during peak hours.

GIS Mapping

Order density and delivery efficiency were mapped across key neighbourhoods in Coimbatore.

Identified Hotspots:

- Gandhipuram
- RS Puram
- Peelamedu
- Saibaba Colony

DISCUSSION

The results of this study offer valuable insights into the operational efficiency and customer experience of Swiggy Instamart’s Q-commerce model in Coimbatore. The discussion below ties the empirical findings to the study’s objectives and situates them within the broader context of the literature reviewed.

Delivery Speed and Logistics Framework

One of the core strengths of Swiggy Instamart identified in the study is its ability to maintain a sub-20-minute delivery average, with over 66% of customers rating delivery time as highly satisfactory. This finding validates the company’s effective use of dark store networks and route optimization technologies, aligning with RevBoosters (2023), who emphasized real-time logistics and predictive analytics as critical to sub-30-minute fulfillment models.

Delivery executives also confirmed that 60% of orders were completed within the 15–20-minute bracket, reinforcing the consistency of Swiggy’s last-mile operations. However, congestion during peak hours and navigation challenges were reported as significant bottlenecks.

Inventory Management and Fulfilment

Swiggy’s inventory management scored a high fulfilment accuracy of 93%, reflecting the efficiency of its AI-driven systems. Customers expressed moderate satisfaction with product availability (mean score: 3.8), highlighting scope for improving SKU diversity at certain locations. This is consistent with WareIQ (2024) and ScienceDirect (2024), which noted that automated shelf optimization enhances inventory turnover but may limit variety due to space constraints in dark stores.

Customer Satisfaction and Influencing Factors

The regression analysis revealed that app experience and delivery speed are the strongest predictors of customer satisfaction—echoing findings from Tandfonline (2023) and Prakash (2024), who noted that interface usability and fulfillment consistency drive loyalty in Q-commerce. The high satisfaction scores among frequent users suggest that Swiggy's value proposition improves with repeated engagement, although cost sensitivity was a deterrent for some first-time users.

Competitive Positioning

Swiggy emerged as the leading platform in terms of delivery speed and customer satisfaction when benchmarked against Zepto and Blinkit. While all three platforms demonstrated operational maturity, Swiggy's integrated infrastructure and tech-enabled logistics gave it a measurable advantage—particularly in high-demand zones. This supports Scripown (2023), which identified Swiggy's operational synergy as a key differentiator in the Indian Q-commerce market.

Seasonal and Spatial Demand Variations

Time series analysis revealed clear patterns in peak demand—both hourly (6–9 PM) and seasonally (festivals). This underscores the need for dynamic resource allocation and localized stocking strategies. GIS mapping further confirmed that delivery performance is geographically uneven, with Eastern Coimbatore lagging

due to limited infrastructure. These findings align with the challenges identified by Gund & Daniel (2024) and Roy & Ranjekar (2023), who emphasized the need for flexible delivery frameworks and regional adaptation in Tier-2 cities.

Operational Challenges and Sustainability

Although Swiggy's logistics model is generally efficient, it is not without limitations. Traffic congestion, variable demand, and delivery executive shortages were commonly reported challenges. Furthermore, environmental concerns—while not quantitatively analyzed in this study—remain relevant, as noted in IGI Global (2024), which calls for eco-conscious fleet strategies and packaging solutions.

FINDINGS

Swiggy Instamart successfully maintains an average delivery time under 20 minutes, with 66% of customers rating delivery speed as satisfactory or very satisfactory.

App usability and delivery speed emerged as the most significant predictors of customer satisfaction, contributing to Swiggy's higher overall satisfaction scores compared to competitors like Zepto and Blinkit.

Inventory fulfillment accuracy stood at an impressive 93%, though product

variety remains a moderate concern for users, especially first-time buyers.

Spatial analysis through GIS identified high-demand delivery zones—such as Gandhipuram, RS Puram, and Peelamedu—and recommended the expansion of dark store infrastructure, particularly in East Coimbatore.

Time series trends showed that peak order volumes align with evening hours and festival periods, emphasizing the need for adaptive inventory and workforce management.

Operational challenges such as traffic congestion, labor shortages, and inconsistent demand patterns continue to hinder seamless last-mile delivery.

SUGGESTIONS

This study contributes to the growing literature on Q-commerce by offering region-specific insights into operational dynamics and consumer behavior in Tier-2 urban settings. It reinforces the role of technology-driven logistics and hyperlocal infrastructure in achieving delivery efficiency and customer loyalty. For practitioners, the findings offer actionable strategies in dark store placement, app design, and resource allocation that can inform the scalable deployment of Q-commerce models beyond metro cities.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the operational effectiveness, customer satisfaction, and strategic logistics framework of Swiggy Instamart's quick commerce model in the Tier-2 city of Coimbatore. Through a robust mixed-method approach and stratified sampling across user groups, the research provided a comprehensive evaluation of how Swiggy Instamart adapts Q-commerce principles to a regional market.

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